

Effect of sodium hypochlorite and EDTA on bonding strength of different adhesives to pulp chamber – An experimental in-vitro Study

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ABSTRACT:

Aim: The Aim of this study is to compare the effect of sodium hypochlorite and EDTA on bonding strength of different adhesives to pulp chamber. **Methodology:** Sixty freshly extracted human molars were collected for the study. Dental calculus was removed, and the teeth were rinsed under running water for 15 seconds, then stored in thymol-saturated saline. The pulp chamber was exposed and the root sectioned 2 mm below the cemento-enamel junction. The pulp tissue was carefully removed and the teeth rinsed with distilled water. The teeth were divided into two groups: NaOCl treatment (3% NaOCl for 20 min) and EDTA treatment (17% EDTA for 20 min), with both groups receiving distilled water rinses. Each group was subdivided into three adhesive subgroups (5th Generation (Bondplus), 6th Generation (3M), & 7th Generation (Manibond), and the bonding agents were applied to the pulp chamber dentin. Resin composite was incrementally placed and light-cured. The teeth were stored in distilled water at 37°C for 24 hours. Afterward, the bonded specimens were sectioned, and three 1 ± 0.05 mm² beams were randomly selected for microtensile bond strength (μ TBS) testing. The bond strength was measured in MPa using a tensile testing apparatus, and failure modes were analyzed via light microscopy and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) after gold-palladium coating. **Results:** Results showed that bond strength increased significantly with advancing bonding agent generations, with the 7th generation exhibiting the highest bond strength in both NaOCl and EDTA groups. EDTA treatment significantly enhanced bond strength compared to NaOCl for all generations ($p < 0.001$). Statistical analysis revealed highly significant differences in bond strength across groups ($F = 1146.482$, $p < 0.001$ for NaOCl and $F = 852.424$, $p < 0.001$ for EDTA). **Conclusion:** In conclusion, EDTA treatment significantly improves bond strength compared to NaOCl, particularly with newer adhesive generations. The 7th generation adhesives showed the highest adhesion, underscoring the importance of optimizing adhesive and pretreatment protocols for durable restorations. Further studies are needed to explore the long-term effects, including microleakage.

Keywords: Bonding agent, NaOCl, EDTA, Composite resin

INTRODUCTION:

Adhesive dentistry has revolutionized restorative techniques by improving esthetics, conserving tooth structure, and reducing microleakage¹. These advancements are particularly significant as patients today are increasingly conscious of dental appearance². Enamel, being 95% mineral by weight, is structurally homogenous, while dentin, with 70% mineral and high organic content, is heterogeneous and moist³⁻⁵. These characteristics make bonding to dentin more challenging. Successful adhesion is critical in endodontics for effective sealing of the pulp chamber.

However, disinfectants like sodium hypochlorite (NaOCl) and EDTA, widely used during root canal therapy, may alter dentin surfaces and affect bonding⁶. NaOCl, with its strong antimicrobial and tissue-dissolving properties, can degrade the collagen matrix, compromising the hybrid layer formation essential for bonding⁷⁻⁹. Etch-and-rinse adhesives, which rely on exposed collagen, are more affected, while self-etch systems may be less impacted¹⁰. EDTA aids in smear layer removal by demineralizing dentin, exposing collagen and improving resin infiltration¹¹. Yet, excessive use can weaken dentin and reduce bond

strength¹²⁻¹³. The interaction of NaOCl and EDTA may further influence adhesive performance¹⁴.

Adhesive systems have evolved across generations, from multi-step total-etch to simplified self-etch approaches¹⁵⁻¹⁶. Fifth-generation systems are considered the benchmark for their ease of use and high bond strength. Adhesives consist of an etchant, primer, and resin, which interact with tooth structures to form a hybrid layer that supports durable bonding¹⁷⁻²². Etch-and-rinse systems require separate etching, while self-etch adhesives combine steps and simultaneously demineralize and infiltrate the dentin²³⁻²⁵.

Bond strength is commonly evaluated through microtensile bond strength (μ TBS), considered the most accurate method, alongside other tests like shear, tensile, and push-out strength¹⁴.

This in-vitro study aims to evaluate the effects of NaOCl and EDTA on the bond strength of various adhesive systems to pulp chamber dentin. Comparing etch-and-rinse and self-etch adhesives will help optimize clinical protocols and improve restorative outcomes in endodontics.

MATERIALS AND METHOD:

This experimental, non-clinical in vitro study was conducted at the Department of Conservative Dentistry and Endodontics, Loni. The objective was to evaluate the bond strength of various adhesive systems following chemical treatment with either sodium hypochlorite (NaOCl) or ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA). A total of 60 freshly extracted, non-carious human permanent molars without visible cracks were collected for the study. All external debris and tissue remnants were removed, and the teeth were disinfected and stored in 0.1% thymol solution at room temperature to prevent microbial growth and preserve dentin structure until further use.

To standardize the preparation, the coronal portions of the teeth were trimmed using a Vernier caliper and sectioned with a diamond disc under constant water irrigation. Enamel was removed 3 mm below the cusp tips, and the pulp chamber was accessed using a gypsum model trimmer. The roots were then sectioned approximately 2 mm below the cemento-enamel junction (CEJ). The pulp tissue was carefully removed using a spoon excavator, ensuring the dentin within the pulp chamber remained intact, and the chambers were rinsed with distilled water to eliminate any residual tissue.

The prepared samples were randomly divided into two main groups based on the chemical treatment applied. In Group 1, the specimens were immersed in 3% NaOCl solution for 20 minutes and subsequently rinsed with distilled water. In Group 2, the specimens were treated with 17% EDTA solution for the same duration and rinsed similarly. Each main group was further divided into three subgroups ($n = 10$), depending on the type of adhesive system used: 5th-

generation (Bondplus, Medicept Dental, UK), 6th-generation (Adper™ Single Bond 2, 3M USA), and 7th-generation (Mani Bond, Mani Medical, Germany). For bonding in the 5th-generation adhesive subgroup, the etch-and-rinse protocol was followed. The dentin was etched with 37% phosphoric acid gel (DPI) for 15 seconds, rinsed thoroughly with distilled water, and gently air-dried to maintain moisture. Bondplus adhesive was then applied uniformly, air-thinned for 5 seconds to evaporate the solvent, and light-cured for 20 seconds. Resin composite (3M ESPE) was placed in 2 mm increments, with each layer light-cured for 20 seconds. In the 6th-generation group, after selective enamel etching for 15 seconds with phosphoric acid, the 3M Adper™ Single Bond 2 adhesive was applied with a microbrush and actively rubbed on the dentin surface for 15–20 seconds. After air-drying for 5 seconds to evaporate the solvent, it was light-cured for 10 seconds, followed by incremental placement and curing of the composite. The 7th-generation group followed an all-in-one approach using Mani Bond. The adhesive was directly applied to the dentin, allowed to react for 20 seconds, gently air-dried, and light-cured for 20 seconds. Composite resin was applied incrementally and cured similarly. All bonded specimens were stored in distilled water at 37°C for 24 hours before testing.

After storage, the bonded teeth were sectioned vertically using a low-speed diamond saw under continuous water irrigation to obtain resin-dentin sticks of 1 ± 0.05 mm² cross-sectional area. The first horizontal cut was made 0.5 mm below the resin surface to remove excess material, followed by three additional cuts to retrieve uniform beams. From each tooth, three beams were randomly selected for micro-tensile bond strength (μ TBS) testing.

Each beam was affixed to a Ciucchi's jig using cyanoacrylate adhesive and subjected to tensile forces using a universal testing machine (Balancing Equipments Pvt. Ltd.) at a crosshead speed of 1 mm/min until failure. Bond strength was calculated in megapascals (MPa) using the formula μ TBS = F/A , where F is the force at failure in Newtons and A is the bonded cross-sectional area in mm². The mean of three readings per tooth was recorded, giving a total of 10 values per group.

Following bond strength testing, fracture surfaces were examined under a light microscope to determine the failure modes. Specimens were then sputter-coated with gold-palladium (AuPd) for 120 seconds and analyzed under a scanning electron microscope (SEM) (Zeiss Digital Microscope) at 10 kV and 300 \times magnification to observe fracture morphology and interfacial characteristics.

RESULTS:

This study evaluated and compared the micro-tensile bond strength of 5th, 6th, and 7th generation bonding agents following dentin surface treatment with either

sodium hypochlorite (NaOCl) or ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA). The results revealed statistically significant differences in bond strength among the different generations of adhesives under both surface conditioning methods.

With NaOCl treatment, the 5th generation bonding agent exhibited a mean bond strength of 49.10 N (SD = 3.00), while the 6th generation showed an improved value of 65.60 N (SD = 7.47). The 7th generation bonding agent demonstrated the highest bond strength, with a mean of 222.60 N (SD = 13.23). One-way ANOVA indicated a highly significant difference among the three groups ($F = 1146.482, p < 0.001$). Post-hoc analysis confirmed that the 6th generation performed significantly better than the 5th ($p = 0.001$), and the 7th generation showed significantly higher bond strength than both the 5th and 6th generations ($p < 0.001$), indicating progressive improvement with newer adhesive systems.

Under EDTA treatment, bond strength increased across all adhesive generations. The 5th generation bonding agent showed a mean of 65.3 N (SD = 7.24), the 6th generation rose to 123.2 N (SD = 11.06), and the 7th generation reached the highest mean bond strength of 299 N (SD = 18.61). One-way ANOVA again showed a statistically highly significant difference ($F = 852.424, p < 0.001$). Post-hoc comparisons revealed significant improvements in each successive generation, with the 7th generation again outperforming both the 5th and 6th ($p < 0.001$). Direct comparisons between NaOCl and EDTA within each generation revealed that EDTA significantly outperformed NaOCl in all cases. For the 5th generation, bond strength increased from 49.10 N to 65.3 N ($p < 0.001$); for the 6th generation, from 65.60 N to 123.2 N ($p < 0.001$); and for the 7th generation, from 222.60 N to 299 N ($p < 0.001$). These findings highlight EDTA's superior ability to enhance dentin bond strength across all generations of bonding agents.

Comparison of effect of NaOCl and EDTA on the bond strength of different adhesives:

Generation of bonding agent	NaOCl		EDTA		p value (unpaired t test)
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
5 th generation	49.10	3.00	65.3	7.24	<0.001**
6 th generation	65.60	7.47	123.2	11.06	<0.001**
7 th generation	222.60	13.23	299	18.61	<0.001**

*Statistically significant

**Statistically highly significant

Scanned electron microscope

Figure 1: Group A-treated with NaOCl

5th generation bondplus

6th generation 3M bond

7th generation Manibond

Figure 2 : Group B - Treated with EDTA

5th Generation bondplus

6th Generation 3M bond

7th Generation Manibond

DISCUSSION:

Adhesive technology has progressed considerably over the last five decades, evolving through multiple generations of bonding agents aimed at enhancing the durability and predictability of resin–dentin bonding. A primary challenge in adhesive dentistry remains the formation of a reliable bond with the two distinct hard tissues—enamel and dentin. While enamel bonding has demonstrated consistent longevity, achieving similar outcomes with dentin is significantly more complex due to its heterogeneous composition and higher organic content. This necessitates the adoption of more sophisticated bonding strategies to achieve effective adhesion²⁶.

The clinical success of resin-based restorations is heavily dependent on the integrity and durability of the bond to the dentin substrate. As adhesive materials have evolved, their bond strength has improved due to advancements in their chemical formulation and adhesion-promoting mechanisms. Bond strength testing, particularly micro-tensile bond strength (μ TBS), serves as a reliable method for evaluating the performance of adhesive systems under simulated clinical conditions⁹.

The current study evaluated the μ TBS of different generations of bonding agents following dentin surface pretreatment with sodium hypochlorite (NaOCl) or ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA). The results

demonstrated that dentin pretreatment significantly influenced the bond strength outcomes. NaOCl was shown to negatively affect bond strength across all adhesive generations. The 5th generation bonding agent demonstrated the lowest bond strength, followed by a moderate increase in the 6th generation and a significant improvement in the 7th generation. These findings suggest that adhesive performance improves with newer-generation formulations, with statistical analyses confirming highly significant differences between the groups.

Supporting this, Dikmen and Tarim (2018) reported reduced bond strength when NaOCl and EDTA were used together, particularly when followed by application of certain adhesives like Single Bond and Xeno 3²⁷. Similarly, Yuan et al. (2023) observed that NaOCl significantly reduced μ TBS for G-Premio Bond and Clearfil Megabond 2, while some adhesives were less affected. Their SEM findings highlighted structural changes in the adhesive layer, reinforcing the importance of selecting adhesives compatible with NaOCl treatment²⁸.

Conversely, EDTA pretreatment yielded a significant improvement in bond strength across all adhesive generations. The 5th generation bonding agent showed enhanced adhesion compared to NaOCl-treated samples, while the 6th and 7th generations exhibited even greater bond strength. Post-hoc comparisons revealed that the 7th generation adhesive consistently outperformed the earlier generations, suggesting a cumulative benefit of improved formulations and effective smear layer removal by EDTA. These findings are in agreement with Chandrashekhar et al. (2018), who reported that the application of sodium thiosulfate and proanthocyanidin after NaOCl and EDTA irrigation significantly improved bond strength in endodontically treated teeth²⁹.

Direct comparison between NaOCl and EDTA treatments confirmed that EDTA consistently resulted in significantly higher bond strengths across all adhesive generations. This aligns with the findings of Stevens et al. (2024), who demonstrated that EDTA was able to reverse the bond-depleting effects of NaOCl in self-etch adhesives, although results in total-etch mode were more variable depending on the adhesive used³⁰.

The superior performance of EDTA can be attributed to its ability to effectively remove the smear layer and expose collagen fibrils without excessive demineralization, thereby allowing better penetration of adhesive monomers and improving micromechanical retention¹¹. In contrast, NaOCl, while valuable for its antimicrobial action, deproteinizes dentin and alters its permeability, potentially limiting adhesive infiltration and hybrid layer formation³¹. Additionally, residual oxygen from NaOCl treatment may inhibit resin polymerization, particularly affecting one-step adhesives like those in the 7th generation³².

For 5th-generation total-etch systems, NaOCl-induced collagen removal can disrupt resin infiltration, while phosphoric acid etching may only partially restore the bonding substrate³³⁻³⁴. Similarly, 6th-generation self-etch systems show reduced efficacy on deproteinized surfaces, and the 7th-generation all-in-one adhesives are most vulnerable due to their reliance on simultaneous etching, priming, and bonding³².

EDTA's role as a chelating agent allows it to dissolve the inorganic components of the smear layer and preserve the collagen network, enhancing bonding across all adhesive systems. In total-etch systems, EDTA enables resin infiltration and hybrid layer formation³⁵, while in self-etch systems, it supports better interaction with the dentin substrate³⁶. For all-in-one adhesives, EDTA's effect is dose- and time-sensitive to avoid over-demineralization³⁷. Thus, while EDTA is broadly beneficial, careful application is necessary to maintain dentin integrity³⁸.

Bond strength tests serve as the benchmark for assessing adhesive performance. While shear bond strength (SBS) tests are simpler, they can produce uneven stress distribution. The μ TBS test is considered the most reliable for dentin bonding studies due to its ability to evaluate small surface areas and promote uniform stress distribution. It often produces failures close to the material's true ultimate strength and provides better insights into adhesive performance³⁹. However, μ TBS results should be interpreted with caution, as bond strength data do not always correlate with microleakage or long-term sealing ability. Nonetheless, improved adhesion via μ TBS evaluation is associated with better marginal integrity, longer restoration lifespan, and enhanced resistance to mechanical stress in clinical applications⁴⁰.

CONCLUSION:

This study highlights the influence of adhesive advancements and dentin pretreatment on bond strength. While sodium hypochlorite (NaOCl) remains essential for its antimicrobial efficacy, it compromises adhesion by altering dentin structure. In contrast, ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) significantly enhances bond strength by effectively removing the smear layer and facilitating adhesive penetration, particularly in newer bonding agent generations.

Microtensile bond strength testing demonstrated superior performance of EDTA-treated dentin, with 7th generation adhesives exhibiting the highest adhesion. However, as bond strength alone does not guarantee long-term clinical success, its correlation with microleakage requires further investigation.

Optimizing adhesion involves selecting appropriate bonding systems and pretreatment protocols. Future research should aim to improve adhesive formulations and explore methods to mitigate NaOCl's adverse effects, ensuring more durable and successful restorative outcomes.

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